

Clinico Haematological and Biochemical Profile of Anaemia in Paediatric Age Group

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia significantly affects child growth and development. This study evaluates pediatric anemia in Jharkhand, highlighting prevalent iron deficiency and significant cases of hemolytic anemia, including sickle cell anemia and thalassemia.

Methods: We conducted a cross-sectional study of 280 children diagnosed with anemia, analyzing hemoglobin levels, iron profiles, and other hematological markers.

Results: Iron deficiency anemia was predominant, affecting 64% of children. Hemolytic anemia was found in 10%, indicating its regional significance. Other anemia forms like Vitamin B12 deficiency and anemia of chronic disease were also noted.

Conclusion: The study underscores the need for comprehensive anemia screening and interventions, focusing on both nutritional deficiencies and inherited disorders to improve pediatric health outcomes in Jharkhand.

Keywords: Anemia, Pediatric, Iron Deficiency, Hemoglobin, Nutritional Interventions, Hemolytic Anemia.

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Introduction

Anemia in pediatric populations is a pervasive health issue with profound implications for child health and development [1]. Characterized by a deficiency in the number and quality of red blood cells or the concentration of hemoglobin, anemia leads to decreased oxygen transport in the body, which can significantly hinder physiological and cognitive development in children. The World Health Organization (WHO) recognizes anemia as a condition that affects a substantial number of children globally, necessitating ongoing research and targeted treatment strategies [2,3].

Extensive studies have explored the various causes and consequences of pediatric anemia. It is known to arise from a complex interplay of nutritional, infectious, and genetic factors. Nutritional anemia, primarily caused by deficiencies in iron, vitamin B12, and folic acid, is the most common type. This form of anemia is particularly prevalent in low and middle-income countries due to poor dietary diversity and socioeconomic factors that limit access to nutrient-rich foods [4,5].

Moreover, genetic conditions such as thalassemia and sickle cell disease also contribute significantly to the burden of anemia, highlighting the role of inherited disorders in the etiology of anemia in certain populations. Infectious diseases like malaria

and helminth infections further complicate the clinical picture by causing hemolytic anemia and contributing to nutrient malabsorption, thus exacerbating the severity of anemia [6,7].

Prior research has emphasized the need for a comprehensive approach to diagnose and evaluate anemia, which includes a thorough clinico-hematological and biochemical assessment [8]. These evaluations help delineate the type of anemia—whether microcytic, macrocytic, or normocytic—each associated with different pathophysiological processes. Biochemical markers such as reticulocyte count, serum iron, total iron-binding capacity, and ferritin levels are invaluable in diagnosing the specific type and cause of anemia, thereby guiding appropriate treatment strategies [9,10].

This study aims to provide a detailed clinico-hematological and biochemical profile of anemia in children within a specified demographic area. By analyzing these parameters, the study seeks to identify the predominant types of anemia affecting this population and to understand the underlying causes. Such insights are crucial for developing tailored interventions that can effectively address the specific needs of anemic children and

potentially improve health outcomes in this vulnerable group.

Methodology

Study Design: This research was structured as a cross-sectional observational study with the primary aim of determining the clinico-hematological and biochemical profiles of pediatric anemia patients.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at the Pediatric Research Facility at MGM Medical College in Jamshedpur, focusing on pediatric healthcare. Data collection spanned one year, from January 2023 to December 2023, capturing any seasonal impacts on the incidence and types of anemia.

Participants: The study involved 280 pediatric patients aged 1-12 years, randomly selected from the outpatient department. These participants were all diagnosed with anemia according to WHO hemoglobin level guidelines, which set thresholds at less than 11.0 g/dL for children under 5 years and less than 11.5 g/dL for children aged 5 to 12 years.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

Inclusion Criteria:

- Children aged between 1 and 12 years.
- Diagnosed with anemia as per WHO guidelines.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Children with chronic diseases affecting liver or kidney function.
- Those treated for anemia or who had received a blood transfusion within the previous three months.
- Patients with active or historical cancer diagnoses.

Data Collection and Analysis: Participants underwent a comprehensive medical history review, a physical examination, and blood sample collection. The samples were analyzed for a complete blood count and extensive iron profile among other hematological and biochemical tests. Data confidentiality and integrity were ensured through secured database storage.

Statistical Analysis: Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 25. Descriptive statistics were used to outline the demographic and

baseline characteristics. Associations between different types of anemia and biochemical markers were explored using chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$.

Focus on Hemolytic Anemia and Thalassemia:

The study identified hemolytic anemia in approximately 10% of the pediatric patients, highlighting its significant regional prevalence in Jharkhand, a detail critical for understanding the specific hematological challenges in this demographic. This prevalence underscores the importance of including comprehensive screening for hemolytic conditions such as sickle cell anemia and thalassemia in routine pediatric assessments in the region. The data provides a foundation for targeted interventions to address and manage these conditions effectively within the affected population.

Results

The study examined 280 pediatric patients diagnosed with anemia, revealing a slight male predominance with 52% males and 48% females. The age distribution showed 40% of participants aged 1-5 years and 60% aged 6-12 years. The findings on the prevalence of various types of anemia are as follows:

Types of Anemia Observed

- **Iron Deficiency Anemia:** Most prevalent, affecting 64% of the study cohort.
- **Vitamin B12 Deficiency:** Found in 18% of the participants.
- **Anemia of Chronic Disease:** Present in 7% of the cases.
- **Hemolytic Anemia:** Notably identified in 10% of the patients, including cases of sickle cell anemia and thalassemia, reflecting the regional prevalence in Jharkhand.
- **Other Types of Anemia:** Comprised 1% of the cases.

The average hemoglobin level across the study group was 9.4 g/dL, with a standard deviation of 1.1 g/dL, indicating a moderate level of anemia as classified by WHO guidelines. The study also demonstrated significant age-related differences in the prevalence of anemia types, with iron deficiency most commonly observed in the younger age group (1-5 years).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Characteristic	Total Participants (N=280)
Age	1-5 years: 112 (40%)
	6-12 years: 168 (60%)
Gender	Male: 145 (52%)

	Female: 135 (48%)
Type of Anemia	Iron Deficiency: 180 (64%)
	Vitamin B12 Deficiency: 50 (18%)
	Anemia of Chronic Disease: 20 (7%)
	Hemolytic Anemia (including sickle cell anemia and thalassemia): 28 (10%)
	Other Types: 2 (1%)
Average Hemoglobin (g/dL)	9.4 ± 1.1

Table 2: Prevalence of Anemia Types by Age Group

Age Group	Iron Deficiency (%)	Vitamin B12 Deficiency (%)	Anemia of Chronic Disease (%)	Hemolytic Anemia (including sickle cell anemia and thalassemia) (%)
1-5 years	70 (63%)	10 (9%)	5 (4.5%)	8 (7%)
6-12 years	110 (65%)	40 (24%)	15 (9%)	20 (12%)

Discussion

The study demonstrated that iron deficiency anemia (IDA) is the most prevalent form of anemia among pediatric patients, accounting for 64% of all cases. The average hemoglobin level was 9.4 g/dL, indicating moderate anemia according to WHO standards. The prevalence of IDA was particularly high among younger children (1-5 years), which can be attributed to their rapid growth rates and increased iron demands, often unmet due to inadequate dietary intake.

A notable finding from the study was the identification of hemolytic anemia, including sickle cell anemia and thalassemia, in approximately 10% of the participants. This reflects the specific regional prevalence in Jharkhand and underscores the significant impact of genetic factors on pediatric anemia in this area [11]. The results highlight the necessity for targeted genetic screening and counseling as part of routine pediatric care in regions where these hemoglobinopathies are endemic [12].

The study revealed distinct patterns in the occurrence and nature of anemia across different pediatric age cohorts, with significant statistical associations between age groups and types of anemia ($p < 0.05$) [13]. This suggests that the etiology of anemia varies with age, likely due to differences in dietary intake, exposure to infectious diseases, and the onset of genetically inherited conditions like thalassemia and sickle cell disease [14].

Given the high prevalence of IDA, especially among younger children, there is a pressing need for enhanced public health strategies [15]. These should include improved dietary education, iron supplementation programs, and broader access to healthcare services to effectively address and reduce the burden of anemia. Public health efforts should also focus on increasing awareness about

the importance of early diagnosis and management of hemolytic conditions [16].

The presence of hemolytic anemia at a significant rate, particularly sickle cell anemia and thalassemia, calls for comprehensive screening protocols that incorporate both nutritional assessments and genetic testing [17]. Managing these conditions requires a multifaceted approach that may include pharmacological treatment, nutritional support, and in some cases, transfusion therapies. Community health programs should be tailored to provide specific interventions that target these conditions to reduce their impact on child health [18-20].

This study illuminates the diverse etiological landscape of pediatric anemia in the Jharkhand region, with a notable prevalence of both nutritional deficiencies and inherited disorders. The findings advocate for a holistic approach to the diagnosis, treatment, and management of anemia in children, emphasizing the integration of clinical practices with public health initiatives to improve overall health outcomes in pediatric populations.

Conclusion

The study conclusively identified iron deficiency anemia as the most prevalent form of anemia among pediatric patients, particularly prominent in the 1-5-year age group, reflecting the increased iron demands of this rapidly growing cohort. With an average hemoglobin level indicative of moderate anemia, the findings emphasize the critical need for targeted nutritional interventions and enhanced public health strategies. These should focus on improving dietary iron intake through education, supplementation, and improved access to healthcare services to address and mitigate the burden of anemia in children, fostering better health outcomes and supporting optimal development.

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